

Developing Pre-Supernova Neutrino Model Support for sntools

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Motivation

Unlike supernova burst neutrinos (SN1987A [1]), **pre-supernova neutrinos** are produced long **before the core collapse** of a massive star and the eventual supernova. Neutrinos from **silicon burning** phases are emitted **days before** the core collapse, with **typical energies of a few MeV**.

Why do we need to detect them?

- Galactic core-collapse supernovae are **very rare and difficult to predict**
- Detection of pre-supernova neutrinos would **provide an early warning**
 - physicists have time to **focus resources** on the observation of this event

Integrating pre-supernova models into a neutrino event generator would help to provide a **unified framework** for studying these neutrinos in current and next generation detectors.

sntools

sntools [2] is a **neutrino event generator for supernova burst neutrinos**, originally developed to study supernova model discrimination with Hyper-Kamiokande [3].

- Provides **realistic detailed event-by-event** supernova neutrino event generation including **timing** and **directional** information for **multiple interaction channels**
 - Enables **more advanced studies** than other currently available open-source software packages
- Supports a range of **detector geometries and materials**
- Supports several different input formats for neutrino fluxes and **can use core-collapse supernova models implemented in SNEWPY** [4]
- The output file can be **directly fed into simulation software** to simulate detector response
- Already used** by several neutrino experiments

Pre-Supernova Neutrino Models

Work has been undertaken to **add support for pre-supernova event generation** into sntools. Initially, **we support four families of pre-supernova models**, re-using their existing and well-tested implementations within SNEWPY.

A graph of the number of IBD events in Hyper-Kamiokande generated by sntools as a function of neutrino energy for 4 different pre-supernova neutrino flux models.

Time Bin Optimisation Study

To make sntools **suitable for processing pre-supernova fluxes**, the **size of the time bins** used during the event rate calculation (1ms for ccsn models) had to be **changed**. A time bin size of 1ms is no longer appropriate as researchers often wish to calculate the pre-supernova neutrino event rate **over several days** before core collapse.

A **time bin optimisation study** was performed, considering a range of factors that affect the accuracy of the event generation process and the ease of use of the software package.

A summary of these factors and the corresponding limits placed upon the time bin size are given in the table below:

Limiting Factor	Limit
Massive Neutrinos (time of flight difference)	>1ms
Memory Usage	>10ms
Run Time	No Limit
Poisson Statistics	>50ms
Rebinning Investigation – capturing event rate rise	<300s
Minimising stepping effect	1s bins limit this effect the best

The **optimal value** was determined as **1 second**. But to provide **flexibility**, the time bin size was made an **optional argument**, with the **default set to 1s**.

Validation

The below plots demonstrate the **internal consistency of sntools** and **show good agreement** with pre-supernova Monte Carlo used for pre-supernova neutrino sensitivity study by **Super-Kamiokande** in 2022 [5].

A graph showing the time profile of IBD events in Hyper-Kamiokande generated by sntools compared to the expected distribution (given as an input to sntools).

A graph showing the comparison of the positron energy spectra for IBD events generated by sntools and the Super-Kamiokande pre-supernova MC events.

Further investigation concluded that **slight differences** in the energy spectra are due to **differing implementations** of the **IBD cross section** and **rejection sampling** methods used to determine the properties of single events.

To access the current release of sntools, use the following URL or scan the QR code:
<https://github.com/SNEWS2/sntools/>

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